

KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA (KP) GENDER PARITY PERFORMANCE: HISTORICAL COMPARISON UNDER MICS KP 2010, 2017 AND 2021 DATA

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ABSTRACT

Pakistan's regions/areas¹, including Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), are struggling to ameliorate the gender disparity harming girls in the primary school education. However, low priorities with a lack of commitments exacerbate disparities disadvantaging girls widely in most of the regions, with a bitter sting for KP. Gender bias also persists enormously at the divisional, district, urban, and rural levels in KP. Neither has a systematic effort been made to examine the Gender Parity (GP) performance of KP nor to make a comparison with other regions/areas of Pakistan. This research study bridges the prevailing research gap. It evaluates the KP's working towards GP and also compares it with Pakistan's regions/areas. KP continues to be the least performing unit among regions/areas of Pakistan as per MICS KP 2010, 2017 and 2021, with a stagnant GP score of 0.80. Thus, KP lacked in the GP as well as in the MDGs 3.1 and SDGs 4.5.1 targets at the provincial and urban-rural levels. It is the 2nd last region in urban areas with a GP score of 0.90, trailing GB (0.87) only. In the rural domain, KP is the 4th best performer with a GPI of 0.80. It leads Balochistan (0.77) and Sindh (0.71), but lacks AJ&K (1.00), Punjab (0.97), and GB (0.87). The girls having illiterate mothers or belonging to the poorest families are the greatest prey of gender disparities, while the girls having mothers with Secondary and Higher secondary education or living in the fourth wealth quintile/richest families, enjoy GP and also attain the SDGs 4.5.1 target in 2017 and 2021. By achieving the SDG 4.5.1 target in 01 of 3 divisions and 5 of 10 districts, KP gets the highest position in Pakistan. In UNESCO's (2010) GPI ranges (0.90 - 1.03), KP stands fourth with 14% and 16% success at the divisional and district levels, leading Balochistan and Sindh regions, but lags behind AJ&K, Punjab and GB. KP's overall passive performance in GP and SDG 4.5.1 may stem from several socioeconomic deterrents and cultural norms. However, better community support, female/mother's education, better teaching-learning environment, upgraded security, female supportive education policies, healthier transport and improved access to school, along with softening of cultural norms, reducing poverty, and educating

¹ Regions include provinces - Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), and Balochistan while areas include AJ&K and Gilgit Baltistan

the illiterate mothers may improve GP in the KP, ensuring its sustainability in primary school education.

Keywords: : Primary school ed Education, Gender Parity (GP), Primary school Net Attendance Rate (NAR), Gender Parity Index (GPI), Gender Disparities, Regions, Areas, Urban and Rural, Divisions and Districts Introduction

INTRODUCTION

Education is a vital input for Human Capital (HC) formation and an important determinant of economic prosperity and the welfare of the masses. It plays a pivotal role in enhancing social inclusion, respect, and dignity and therefore, pays a substantial dividend in socioeconomic development. Both education access and quality have a direct link to the development of any nation. A nation having quality HC is mostly seen as a developed country (Khan 2011; Imran, 2017; Khan 2017; Khan, 2023; Kazmi et al., 2023a&b; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025; Akram, 2024). Therefore, investing in HC formation accelerates a country's growth and economic prosperity. Both Health and Education are vital for Human Resource Development (HRD), wherein education nurtures growth by upgrading individuals' knowledge, abilities and skills, virtually essential for quality manpower having critical thinking, entrepreneurship and innovation, key to socio-economic development envisaged by individuals and society (Kazmi, 1995 & 1998; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). However, the historical allusion views education as a passive investment in return. Therefore, it continued to be ignored until 1970, presuming indirect benefits under a trickle-down effect of investing in physical capital. Nevertheless, the catastrophe of this hypothetical postulation promoted direct investment in social sectors, particularly in health and education for Human Resources Development, where the growth of primary school education is seen as an agent of economic prosperity and the well-being of the public and society. It enhances individual efficiency, productivity, and thus diminishes dependence on social capital. It also curbs gender bias harming females and ensures a better female role in developing countries and their regions/areas (Kazmi, 2005 & 2010; Shabbir & Wei, 2014 & 2015; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). Nevertheless, the share of women in education in

Pakistan and its regions/areas has remained small since 1947. But a few policy initiatives undertaken in the near past helped even out the gender disparities disadvantaging girls in Pakistan and its regions (Ailaf Ailaan, 2015a&b; PAGE 2021a-e; WEF, 2022; Baran and Bend, 2023; Kazmi et al., 2023a&b; Noreen, 2023).

The Gender Parity (GP²) in primary school education is a common method for measuring the education ranking of an area, while the GPI (Gender Parity Index) is a common instrument for gauging any gain or loss in GP. It determines the education status of an area and also helps to make regional comparisons (World Bank, 2012 & 2018; UNESCO, 2005, 2010 & 2022; Swenson, 2017; UNICEF, 2020; Kazmi et al., 2023 b; WHO, 2023). UNESCO (2010) takes GPI as a "Ratio of female to male values of a given indicator" obtained by dividing the female value of an indicator by its male value. The GP Index/Score "1.00" or within 0.97 -1.03 refers to GP (UNESCO 2010, p. 2). A GPI < 0.97 means a gender gap harming the girls, while a GPI > 1.03 shows a gender bias stinging the boys. The existence of GPI "1.00" or 0.97 - 1.03 refers to GP or absence of gender discrimination in education with enhanced females' role for better social standing and empowerment (WEF, 2022; Kazmi et al., 2023b; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). A very small women's share is evident in every sector of Pakistan and its regions/areas, wherein the education sector is the prime victim and thus, too weak to access the GP score (GPI 1.00) in Pakistan and provinces, particularly in KP (Farooq and Kia, 2016; Kazmi et al., 2023, 2024, & 2025). A small girl's share in primary education is virtually a denial of women's education. It has been aggravating the gender disparities, persistently harming girls in regions/areas. Lacking financial allocations, limited access, poor environment, and weak capacity, as well as persistently delayed development process toll any

² Hereafter, GP refers to Gender Parity in Net Enrolment Ratio (NER) or Net Attendance Rate (NAR).

effort for GP attainment in regions/areas (CIET, 1997; Yousaf, 2013; Farooq and Kai, 2016; Kazmi et al., 2022&25). KP is a victim of a similar dilemma, and the merging of the FATA districts makes the situation more critical. The development process has helped address the Gender gap harming girls since the early 1970s³ In Pakistan's regions/areas, including KP (Kazmi et al, 2024 &25). However, empirical evidence on GP performance towards GP in KP and its standing in the regions/areas is either rare or non-existent. This primary research study fills the prevailing research gap by examining and comparing the GP achievements of KP with other regions/areas using MICS KP data (rounds 4,5 &6) obtained in 201, 2017 and 2021. It also finds KP's performance in terms of GP with segregation at urban-rural, divisional, and district levels. It also explores factors hindering KP in attaining GP, especially referring to MDGs 3.1 and SDGs 4.5.1.

1.1. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

KP faces numerous challenges in establishing a robust educational sector. A few girls' schools with missing basic facilities, further compounded by natural and manmade hazards⁴, undermine KP's efforts for early attainment of GP. So far, no research effort has been conducted to examine the KP profile with segregation at urban-rural, divisional and district levels. Lack of evidence-based research on gender parity in urban-rural areas, divisions, and districts in KP is, therefore, a serious concern. To bridge this research gap, the study explores KP's working towards GP attainment in the province with division, district and urban-rural segregation. It also compares the KP profile with other regions in GP concerning MDGs 3.1 and SDGs 4.5.1. The study enlists factors hindering KP performance towards the early attainment of GP in KP.

1.2 Methodology

This research initiative benefits from Secondary data obtained from KP's Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys, wave 4, 5 & 6. It deploys renowned statistical packages (SPSS-26 and MS Excel) to conduct data analysis and calculate GP

at urban/rural, division and district levels. Different graphical tools are deployed to display the occurrence of gender parity or disparity in KP with segregation of urban/rural, division and district domains. In particular, the GP is examined from the divisional and district perspectives to determine outperforming and underperforming divisions and districts in KP with regional/area comparisons.

1.3 Objectives of the Study:

- Examine the KP education sectors' working towards GP at the primary school level;
- Compare divisional and district performance to determine outperforming and slow-working divisions and districts
- Examines/compares KP's working towards MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1 targets and 5 provinces/areas in Pakistan.
- Identify outperforming and passive divisions and districts in KP in accessing GP
- Identify factors hindering KP from getting the targeted GP score

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The failure of trickle-down supposition in the 1970s led to invest in HRD (Human Resource Development) and basic needs through education and health for enhancing economic growth, upgrading HR quality and thus improving life of the common man (Kazmi, 1995 & 2010; Rahman and Uddin, 2009; Umer and Zahid, 2017; Kazmi et al., 2023a&b; Kazmi et al., 2024). Educational development is instrumental for economic growth, leading to a prosperous, happy, and peaceful life (Knowles & Maddison, 2002; Singh, 2018). Pouring money into education improves the socio-economic standings of an individual, area and society (Kazmi, 1995; Kazmi et al., 2023a & b)

Gender parity (GP) in primary school education (Net Attendance Rate/NAR) is a vital tool for comparing the educational standing of a region/area. Mostly the developing countries,

³ After the separation of East Pakistan

⁴Refugee Inflow, militancy in Swat, Wana and other areas of KP, Deadly Earthquake 2005, Floods in 2010 & 2022 and COVID-19, etc.

along with their regions/areas, are victims of gender disparity, disadvantaging girls except Maldives, Sri Lanka, Kerala in India, Somalia, Cuba, and Vietnam, getting a healthy GP score even with weak economic status (WEF, 2022; Iqbal, 2022; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). Education in Pakistan is a neglected area with a low allocation of 2.5% of GDP (UNESCAP, 2018), implying the MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1 attainment. With a GP (GPI 0.841), it led Afghanistan (GPI 0.44) only. According to WEF (2022), it may take decades (12-15) to cover the prevailing gender gap harming girls. Therefore, Iqbal (2022) suggests realigning policies, standards, and strategies helpful in getting different domains - economy, health, and education - with a precise emphasis on GP at the primary level. Baran and Bend (2023) suggest improving public-private partnerships (PPP), girls' schools and female teachers, GDP allocations (4.5%) for education, family support, female security and transport to reverse the situation. Yusauf, Saher (2013), using MICS Punjab 2007-8 data, examines the Gender Gap in primary school education in Punjab and finds a strong pro-male bias in total primary school enrolment. In disaggregated terms, the urban areas have marginal pro-female biases against rural areas. The cultural attributes were the strong factors behind the GP matrix, along with the mother's education and family opulence. Umer, Madia and Zahid, Asger (2017) find a lack of SDG 4.5.1 at national, regional, and district levels, along with rural areas, which could not be achieved by Pakistan until 2030 without focusing on Baluchistan. They suggest policy realignment and more financial and other inputs, along with better, healthier government and community support. Imran, Mohammad (2017) and PAGE (2021d) studies do not find a single district in Punjab getting UNESCO's (2010) assigned GP score (0.97-100), exhibiting a wide gender gap harming girls in districts. Govt. of Punjab (2022) report on Gender Parity, "Punjab Gender Parity Report (PGPR) 2021," while discussing the GPI enrolment in Punjab's districts reveals that 17 districts exhibit witnessed a female-dominated trend in enrolment in 2021 against 15 districts in FY 2019-20 wherein Sahiwal and Hafizabad witnessed perfect parity in enrolment, a considerable achievement as disproportionate enrolment in any gender is undesirable and thus

be promoted through instrumental measures - community support, political commitment, female proactive role in family, greater budget and public private partnership (PPP), etc. Abdul Rashid and his colleagues (2012) investigate MDG 3.1 attainment in the district of Quetta, Balochistan find an enormous gender disparity harming girls due to missing facilities in schools, needing improvement with the provision of more funding and allied inputs. PAGE report (2021b) also finds a wide variation in GP at the district level in Balochistan, having district Sohbatpur as the best performer (GPI 0.89) while district Sherani is the lowest performer (GPI 39.93). Mohsin's study (2023) witnesses Balochistan as the lowest performer in the world, having only 27% of literate women (only 2% in rural areas) along with 83% out-of-school girls, which is due to restricted domestic life, limited access, strict cultural norms/local traditions, a lack of security, early marriages, etc. The CIET International Sindh Report (1997) finds a wider gender gap in rural areas than in urban areas. It suggests more parent education focusing on > mother schooling and mother say in the family, community support, < missing facilities, and more girls' schools and female teachers, along with special policy interventions - free Books, Meals, and uniforms with judicious distribution. Brohi and Kakepoto (2013) find that gender bias is harming girls in Pakistan and its rural areas, especially in Sindh province. Overcoming this situation, they suggest instant handling of financial scarcity, cultural binding, a weak education system, a lack of government commitment, and a community role. Zulqurnain and Hussain (2016) examine the contrast between Pakistan and its provinces. Among the 100 girls enrolled in public sector primary schools in Pakistan, Balochistan share 3%, Sindh 13%, KP 24%, and Punjab 51%, exhibiting a wide gender gap harming girls in three provinces, mainly due to the missing facilities in schools and limited access. The PAGE report (2021e) finds Sindh lacking GP attainment in all districts, with some variations - district Dadu leads (GPI 90.39) while district Sajawal is at the tail (GPI 69.91). Azad Jammu & Kashmir outstrips regions/areas in education indicators in Pakistan (Shabbier and Wei, 2015; Farooq and Kai, 2016; and Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). Farooq and Kia (2016) find AJ&K with a GPI of 0.95, a GP at the state level

with some small district-level variations. PAGE's (2021a) study for AJ&K and Gilgit-Baltistan (GB) offers district-wise education data and witnesses some gender disparities at the division and district levels in AJ&K against a big gender gap at both these levels in GB. Kazmi et al. (2023a) find AJ&K proactive in attaining the SDG 4.5.1 target (GPI 1.00) along with UNESCO's (2010) given range (0.97-1.03). Kazmi et al. (2023b) study also builds a historical account of GP in AJK using MICS AJ&K 2008 and MICS AJ&K 2020-21 data. They find AJ&K's vibrant progress in getting GP referring to MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1 as well as at the division, district, urban and rural areas level. However, girls with illiterate mothers or residents of the poorest households are persistently victims of gender discrimination, disadvantaging them even in 2021. The above-stated gains in AJ&K occurred due to vigorous government initiatives, a proactive community role, soft cultural norms, easy access to school, more girls' schools and female teachers, and provision of co-education, etc.

Haq, Ijaz. Ul's (2016) study for Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) infers that females constitute a marginalised segment of the population experiencing a significant gender gap in all educational indicators. He observes public school enrollment, for boys and girls 66% and 34%, against private school enrollment for boys is 68% and girls 32%, respectively. Linking this big gender gap with numerous factors -financial scarcity, sociocultural norms, son preference, and limited access to schools - he suggests more funding for girls' education, a greater government and community role, additional poverty-eradicating measures and extra girl-favouring education policies along with wider campaigns for girls' education. UNWOMEN's study (2020) for KP finds that the overall education system in the selected Newly Merged Districts (NMDs - Bajaur, Mohmand, Khyber, Orakzai, Kurram, North Waziristan, and South Waziristan (Upper and Lower) of KP is in shambles. The study referred FDIHS - 2013-14 (FATA Development Indicators Household Survey (2013-14) to cite that only 33.3 % of population (10 years and above) is literate, compared to 53% in KP and 58% in Pakistan, while women's literacy rate is 13%, which is lower than KP (30%) and Pakistan (47%). It finds many hundreds of thousands of out-of-school (OOS) girls and boys, besides an

extremely high dropout rate of girls in primary school education. The study discovers five major challenges tolling girls' schooling and their access to education: a) Intra-household discriminatory practices relying exclusively on son preference considering boys an asset against girls a liability; b) Early girls marriages, a strong instigator of girls school dropout; c) Restricted mobility due to cultural biddings, security reasons and harassment, discouraging families to risk for female education; d) A few schools with deficient physical facilities and access, particularly for girls; and e) Lacking female faculty with deficient skill and competency. PAGE's (2021c) study for KP finds a big gender gap at the primary and secondary levels. At the secondary level, GPI declines from 0.60 in 2019-20 to 0.58 in 2020-21, but at the primary school level, it remains at 0.76 in the year 2020-21. Among the districts, only Abbottabad gains GP with a GPI of 0.97, while Hangu is at the tail with a GP score of 0.38. Noreen, Amna (2023) infers that Gender inequality is a serious issue and a social evil, hindering socioeconomic progress in KP. It implies females' growth and development, and thus hinders their progress at the provincial level. Despite Pakistan and its region's multifaceted moves, the women's suffering persists even in 2023, she added. To her, this widely prevailing discrimination and oppression in KP have been tolling females' potential, rights, inspiration, and strength. She infers that this is mainly because of hostile trends - patriarchal mindset, cultural norms, strict social bindings, female confinement at home, missing female role in home and public life, girls' limited access to education, health, and job openings, illiteracy, and lack of awareness. She further argued that a lack of education enhances their vulnerability towards exploitation and abuse. She infers that averting these pitfalls needs instant handling through the collective efforts of individuals, government and society. It also needs to alter primitive mindsets and cultural norms by promoting education and awareness, with strict law enforcement to protect women's rights. Kazmi et al. (2024) find that AJ&K, by attaining a GPI of 1.00, outstrips Pakistan (GPI 0.84) and some of its neighbouring/South Asian countries. They find KP as the least performer in GP at the regional level, while 3rd best in urban areas and 2nd last in the rural vicinity and quality education, mainly

due to the district in FATA districts, e.g. North Waziristan, with a GPI of 0.20, hosts 80 OOS girls against 100 boys in school. Another study by Kazmi et al. (2025) finds KP as the lowest performer in MICS5 KP with a GPI of 0.80 (MICS KP 2017). It remains the lowest performer under MICS5 and MICS6 KP, having a GPI of 0.80 with a wide variation in GPI at urban (0.90) and rural (0.77) areas. It also fails to get the earmarked score (GPI 1.00) in most of the divisions and districts. Only one division 14% and 5 districts (16%) gain the SDGs 4.5.1 target, placing it in 4th position in Pakistan. Kazmi, referring to Farooq and Kia (2016), cites the GP of FATA districts (Bajaur, Mohmand, Khyber, Orakzai, Kurram, North Waziristan, and South Waziristan) 0.52 against 0.69 in KP in 2010 -11. After merging as Newly Merged Districts (NMDs), KP has persistently been holding a GP of 0.80 since 2010 (MICS KP 2010), having implications for the future GP profile in KP.

The literature evaluation presents a good understanding of regional/area efforts for redressing gender disparities harming girls in KP. However, the historical snapshot mainly fails to make any GP regional comparisons with a focus on KP, since the holding of MICS surveys in the provinces/areas in the new millennium. It rarely explores the regional profile using MICS data, except for Punjab, which has merely one or two studies. In KP, no investigation based on MICS data has been made to examine GP working at its regional, urban-rural, divisional, and district levels. This research study work, “**Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) Gender Parity Performance: Historical Comparison Using MICS KP Round 4, 5 and 6 Data**”, is virtually an opening designed to bridge the prevailing research gap. The study examines and compares KP’s efforts in meeting international commitments - MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1, along with other regions/areas in Pakistan. It also examines urban-rural, district and divisional

working in GP attainment as per the committed goals or UNESCO’s (2010) criteria. The study also makes a prudent effort to enlist factors helping or obstructing the attainment of GP targets, especially MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1 targets in KP.

3. ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

This first-ever research study explores the Gender Parity profile of KP and its standing among the regions/areas of Pakistan regarding MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1. Using MICS KP (2010, 2017 & 2021) data, it explores KP’s work for attaining these targets in the given timeframe, 2015 and 2030. The comparative analysis of different MICS KP data witness that KP gradually works towards GPI though with a slow pace for removing gender disparities disadvantaging girls under numerous adversities - strict cultural norms, restricted female role, economic hardships, refugees inflow, militancy, security threat, lethargic community, difficult access, insufficient number of girls’ school and female faculty and delicate education policies/systems, mainly relying on federal government along with inadequate funding, fragile education environment, lacking transport facilities, patriarchy, son preference, patriarchal mindset etc., (Khan, 2011; Haq, 2016; Khan, 2017; UNWOMEN, 2020, Noreen, 2023; Kazmi et al., 2024 and 2025). Table 3.1 demonstrates KP’s overall performance in GP under the MICS KP rounds 4, 5, & 6 held in 2010, 2017 and 2021, respectively. Despite numerous policy and program initiatives along with planned interventions, the GP score in KP remains static at 0.80 in MICS KP 2010 and thereafter, in 2017 and 2021, indicating some critical bottlenecks in redressing gender disparity harming girls. The results indicate that KP, as a region, not only fails to achieve MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1 targets but also has continuously been hosting 20 OOS girls against 100 boys in school since 2010 (Table 3.1).

Area	MICS KP 2010 Round 4	MICS KP 2017 Round 5	MICS KP 2021 Round 6
Total	0.80	0.80	0.80
Urban	0.95	1.00	0.90
Rural	0.76	0.80	0.80

Source: Prepared from MICS KP 2010, p-59.; MICS KP 2017, P-158; MICS KP 2021, p-290

Table 3.1 also demonstrates KP's virtual performance towards GP in total in the MICS KP 3 rounds held in the last decades. During these three exercises, the GP score of 0.80 remains unchanged, referring to persistent girls suffering with 20 OOS girls against 100 boys in school. The results also indicate that KP fails to achieve internationally committed targets. It observes persistent gender disparities (GPI 0.80) harming girls for more than ten years, i.e. from 2010 to 2021 (Table 3.1). This may be due to the low priority given to the KP's education sector in previous decades, which has kept the education indices stagnant or slow, particularly in gender parity (0.80) at primary school education, as reflected in Table 3.1. A persistent total GP score of 0.80 in MICS KP 3 rounds speaks for KP government apathy in redressing gender disparities disadvantaging girls since 2010.

3.1 Urban-Rural Wise Gender Parity in KP

The prevalence of Gender Parity in urban and rural areas determines the female profile, indicating better quality of life in a nation as well as in its provincial/regional setups (Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). This research study examines the GP prevalence in KP with segregation at the urban and rural levels. Despite urban areas hosting better Public and Private education facilities, serving the elite, bureaucrats and privileged class, Table 3.1 shows that the urban zones of KP lacked GP and MDG 3.1 in 2010. A GPI of 0.95 refers to gender bias against girls, although Farooq and Kia (2016) take this score as a gender parity being close to the UNESCO (2010) GPI range (0.97-1.03). Under MICS5 KP 2017, KP had gained 0.05 Percentage points, pushing its GPI to 1.00, referring to a precise Gender parity and thus early attainment of the SDG 4.5.1 target in urban areas of KP, i.e. 13 years before its deadline (2030). However, it could not be maintained in the MICS KP 2021 and dropped to 0.95 in 2021, indicating a reversal in the SDG 4.5.1 target's attainment with a 0.05 Percentage point loss (MICS6 KP 2021). Therefore, the suffering of girls in KP's urban areas was reiterated by hosting 10 girls OOS against 100 boys in the school in 2021. An adverse trend, indicating a 0.025 Percentage points yearly loss in GPI during 2017- 2021, may imply the timely (2030) attainment of the SDG 4.5.1 in urban areas of KP. In the period beyond

2017, the situation indicates that the efforts for achieving the SDG 4.5.1 targets are becoming futile and unproductive.

On the other hand, the rural areas' Gender parity attainment in KP at the Primary school level is entirely different from urban vicinities. The segregated comparison of GP accounts under KP's MICS4, MICS5 and MICS6 offers dissimilar results from those of urban areas. The GP score of 0.76 in rural areas of KP in 2010 (MICS KP 2010) demonstrates the prevalence of wide gender disparities, indicating 25 OOS rural girls against 100 boys in school. It is far away from the target of MDG 3.1 and UNESCO's (2010) given score (0.97-1.03). MICS KP next round (2017) observes a GPI of 0.80, which shows a 0.05 percentage points gain, but it remains deficient in the GP earmarked by UNECSO's (2010) score along with the SDG 4.5.1 target. It also shows the prevalence of the gender disparity, persistently harming rural girls, with 20 OOS girls against 100 boys in school. In short, the comparison of historical data reveals that KP fails to obtain substantial gains in GP at the provincial and urban-rural areas level. It remains incapable of meeting national/international pledges towards MDG 3.1 & SDG 4.5.1, and UNESCO's (2010) given score (GPI 0.97 - 1.03), with a few exceptions in urban areas during 2017 (MICS KP 2017). This odd situation demands a detailed study to explore the limitations that make KP the poorest in Pakistan and inactive in eliminating gender disparities harming girls in the province and urban-rural areas.

Figure 3.1 is a visual demonstration of KP's slow moves in getting GP since the occurrence of the MICS KP 2010. KP neither meets MDG 3.1 nor gets SDG 4.5.1 at the provincial and urban-rural levels. However, the urban areas in KP under MICS KP 2017 attained a GP score of 1.00 against GPI 0.80 in 2010 and successfully achieved the SDG 4.5.1 target. In the next MICS KP in 2021, it reverted to GPI 0.80 with 20% loss, indicating 20 OOS girls against 100 boys in school, like in MICS KP 2010. The rural areas with a GPI of 0.76 were found to be weaker than urban areas, although they observed a GPI of 0.80, having a 0.04 percentage points gain in 2017, with the sustainability of it (0.80) in 2021. The average GP score of 3 KP MICS (2010, 2017 and 2021) is 0.80 total, 0.95 in urban areas and 0.786 in rural areas, referring to the greatest

suffering for rural girls in segregated terms, with almost 21 girls OOS instead of 20 in KP and 0.05

in its urban areas against 100 boys in school (Figure 3.1).

3.2 Divisional Level Gender Parity in KP:

Divisional data reveal that KP obtains mixed results in accessing GP at the divisional level. All seven divisions witness no change in GPI, except a 0.01 percentage point gain in Mardan and D.I. Khan divisions (each), while a 0.01 Percentage

point decline in Peshawar division, reflected in Table 3.2. The Rest of the 4 divisions - Banu (0.6) and Hazara, Khot and Malakand - retained their GP score (0.80 each) in both surveys, as shown in Figure 3.2.

Table 3.2: Divisional Comparison Gender Parity in KP - MICS5 &6

MICS Surveys	DIVISIONs						
	Bannu	GI Khan	Hazara	Kohat	Malakand	Mardan	Peshawar
MICS5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.9
MICS6	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	1.0	0.8

Source: Prepared from MICS KP 2010, p-59; MICS KP 2017, p-158; MICS KP 2021, p-290

In disaggregation terms (MICS KP rounds 5 and 6), the Mardan division leads with an improvement of 0.10 Percentage points, indicating the prevalence of gender parity that fulfils the SDG 4.5.1 target. Peshawar division is next with a GPI of 0.90 under MICS KP 2017, which dropped to a GPI of 0.80 in MICS KP 2021, indicating a widening of the gender gap, harming girls by 0.10 percentage points in 2021.

Moreover, KP experiences 20 OOS girls in 2023 compared to 10 in the MICS KP 2017, against 100 boys in the school. D.I. Kahn also observed some 0.01 percentage point improvement in 2021 compared to 2017, but stands deficient in GP attainment with a GPI of 0.80. However, the extent of OOS girls in D.I Kahn drops from 30 to 20 OOS girls against 100 boys in the school (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Divisional Comparison GP in KP - MICS 5&6

In disaggregation terms, under the MICS KP rounds 5 and 6 portrayed in Figure 3.2, the Mardan division in KP takes the lead, by improving GPI from 0.90 to 1.00 at the primary school level, indicating the prevalence of gender parity and fulfilment of the SDG 4.5.1 target. Peshawar division is the next with GP scores of 0.90 and 0.80, respectively, observing gender disparity harming girls. It also suffers from a 0.10 Percentage points decline in 2021 compared to MICS KP 2017. Moreover, D.I. Kahn also observed a 0.10 percentage points gain in GPI, indicating a reduction in girls suffering from 30 to 20 OOS girls against 100 boys in school. On the other hand, Bannu, Hazara, Khot, and Malakand divisions maintained their status quo with a GPI of 0.80 in both surveys, referring to 20 OOS girls against 100 boys in 2017 and 2021, as visualized in Figure 3.2.

3.3 District Level Gender Parity in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP):

The gender parity contours of KP's districts are illustrated in Figure 3.3, prepared using data from the MICS KP 2010, 2017 and 2021. The MICS KP 2010 data show that only one district, Abbottabad, with a score of 1.03, attains gender

parity. It also gets the MDG 3.1 target 5 years before the end time of 2015. District Haripur with a GPI of 0.95 is next to it, but it lacks in GP. However, in Farooq and Kia's view, it is close to the UNESCO (2010) range of 0.97-1.03 and thus can be taken as GP. All other districts except Bannu witness a GPI of between 0.68 and 0.73, referring to big Gender disparities disadvantaging girls with 22 to 32 OOS girls against 100 boys in school. Bannu is the lowest performer, having a GPI of 0.54, hosting 46 OOS girls against 100 boys in school. Under the MICS KP 2017, Abbottabad retains its first position with a score of 1.00, confirming gender parity at the primary school level along with the SDG 4.5.1 target attainment. Mardan (0.99) is next to it, followed by Chitral and Karak with a GP index of 0.97 each, confirming gender parity in 16% districts, including Abbottabad (UNESCO, 2010). The rest of the 21 (84%) districts in 2017 are victims of gender disparities, harming girls. Among these, ten (10) districts gained GP scores between 0.83 and 0.94. Lower Dir and D.I. Khan each get GPI 0.72, while Sawat, Tank, Tor Ghar and Upper Dir gain a uniform GP score of 0.70, followed by LakiMarwat, Bata Gram and Shangla with a

Table 3.3 District-wise Gender Parity (GP) in KP As Per MICS KP 2010, 2017 and 2021

S.#	District	MICS 2010	MICS 2017	MICS 2021	S.#	District	MICS 2017	MICS 2021
1	Abbottabad	1.03	1	1	17	Mardan	0.99	0.9
2	Bannu	0.54	55	0.6	18	Nowshera	0.87	0.9
3	Batagram	-	0.62	0.6	19	Peshawar	0.87	0.9
4	Buner	-	0.91	0.8	20	Shangla	0.6	0.6
5	Charsadda	0.68	0.83	0.9	21	Swabi	0.9	1

6	Chitral	0.7	0.97	1	22	Swat	0.7	0.8
7	D. I. Khan	0.69	0.72	0.9	23	Tank	0.7	0.7
8	Hangu	-	0.5	0.6	24	Tor Ghar	0.7	0.6
9	Haripur	0.95	0.93	1	25	Up Dir	0.7	0.8
10	Karak	0.7	0.97	0.9	26	Bajaur	-	0.4
11	Kohat	0.73	0.92	0.8	27	Khyber	-	0.5
12	Kohistan	-	0.32	0.3	28	Kurram	-	0.7
13	Lakki Marwat	-	0.63	0.6	29	Mohmand	-	0.4
14	Lower Dir	-	0.72	0.9	30	North Waziristan	-	0.2
15	Malakand Protected Area	-	0.94	1	31	Orakzai	-	0.5
16	Mansehra	-	0.89	0.9	32	South Waziristan	-	0.6

Sources MICS KP 2010, P-169 MICS KP 2017, P.290, and MICS KP 2021, p.678

GPI of 0.62, 0.63 and 60, respectively. Hangu with a GPI 0.50 is the 2nd last, followed by Kohistan (GPI 0.32), the lowest performer in mitigating gender disparities harming girls in 2017 (Table 3.3). Data from the MICS KP 2021 (Table 3.3) also confirms that Abbottabad retains its top position won in 2010 and 2017. It stands as the best performer along with Chitral, Haripur, Malakan Protected Area and Sawabi with a GPI of 1.00 (each). These five districts (almost 13%) achieved gender parity (1.00) and successfully attained the SDG 4.5.1 target in 2021, virtually 09 years earlier than the end time, 2030. The rest of the 27 (87%) in KP's 32 districts with a GPI > 0.97 suffer from gender disparities harming girls. Among these 9 (29%) gained a GPI score of 0.90, 4 (almost 13%) got GPI 0.80, Kuram and Tank (6%) each got GPI 0.70, while 07 (almost 23%) - Bannu, Batagram, Hangu, Lakki Marwat, Shangla, Tot Ghar and South Waziristan - got GPI 0.60 each. Kyber and Orakzai districts got 0.50 each, while Bajuar and Mahmand attained 0.40. (each). Kohistan with GPI 0.30 maintained its 2nd last position in MICS KP round 6 (2021). North Waziristan, as reflected in Table 3.3, is the lowest performer

with a GPI of 0.20 in KP, indicating that 80 OOS girls against 100 boys in school. Newly Meagered Districts (NMDs), along with working in remote districts, may contribute to the overall GP score (0.80) in KP (Kazmi et al., 2025).

3.4 Mother Education and Gender Parity in MICS KP

The Education of Mothers is a vital input for promoting Gender Parity in primary education in an area like KP. The girls with an illiterate mother are extreme victims of gender discrimination in KP, with a GP score between 070 -80 in all three MICS KP exercises, but their suffering declined by 0.05 - 0.10 percentage points in MICS KP 2021. Moreover, the girls having a mother with primary education also suffer from gender disparities in the MICS KP 2010 and 2021, but enjoy parity in the MICS KP 2017 (Table 3.3 and Fig. 3.4). However, the girls with mothers having Secondary and Higher secondary education witness GP in the MICS KP 2017 and 2021 and also attain the SDG 4.5.1 target in 2017 and 2021, with a small 0.01 Percentage points accusive gains favoring of girls under MICS KP 2021

Table 3.4: Role of Mother Education and Wealth Quintile in Gender Parity in KP

Head	Mother's Education/ Wealth Quintile	MICS4 KP Survey 2010	MICS5 KP Survey 2017	MICS6 KP Survey 2021
Mother Education	None	0.75	0.70	0.80
	Primary	0.88	1.00	0.90
	Middle	-	0.90	0.90
	Secondary	1.09	1.00	1.01

	Higher Secondary	-	1.00	1.01
Wealth Quintile	Poorest	0.57	0.60	0.60
	Second	0.70	0.80	0.80
	Middle	0.77	0.80	0.90
	Fourth	0.91	0.90	1.01
	Richest	1.00	1.00	1.00
Source: MICS KP 2010, p.; MICS KP 2017, P-158; MICS KP 2021, p-290				

While the girls having mothers with a Secondary School Certificate with GPI 1.09 in MICS KP 2010 outnumbered the boys with 109 girls against 100 boys in school, indicating the existence of gender bias disadvantaging boys, instead with implications for child labour or child abuse (Guarcello et al., 2014; Kazmi et al., 2025).

Figure 3.3 demonstrates that girls having illiterate mothers are the extreme victims of gender disparities as observed in all three MICS Survey exercises (Kazmi, 2023a&b). It further reveals that the gender disparities harming girls decline

with an increase in mothers' education. Girls having mothers with primary education gain GP 1.00 in 2017 (MICS KP 2021), accessing the SDG 4.5.1 target. Moreover, girls' mothers holding secondary and higher secondary education helps KP in suppressing gender disparities harming girls. It also enables KP to achieve the desired Gender Parity score (1.00) while surprisingly the SDG 4.5.1 target (MICS KP 2017) and with a small 0.01 percentage points additional gains in GP (1.01) under MICS KP 2021.

3.5 Wealth Quintile-wise Gender Parity in AJ&K

Table 3.4 also contains data on Wealth Quintile and Gender Parity in KP, indicating that both boys and girls living in the richest households not only enjoy gender parity with a GPI 1.00 but also meet MDG 3.1 and the SDG 4.5.1 targets under the MICS KP 2010, 2017 and 2021. In addition, students in the fourth quintile under MICS KP 2017 also enjoy Gender Parity with a GPI (1.01) and are slightly above the precise SDG 4.5.1 target. The girls living in the poorest and second, third and fourth Walth Quintiles mostly suffer from gender disparity to varying extents (Yusauf, 2013; Kazmi et al., 2023a&b). Among these, the

poorest segment of girls' students is the greatest victim of gender disparities in all three MICS KP, with a GP score of 0.57 and 0.60, respectively, indicating 40 to 43 OOS girls against 100 boys in school. In the other three Wealth Quintiles, the gender disparities disadvantaging girls also persist, with a GPI varying between 0.70 and 0.91 in MICS KP 2010 and 2017. Overall, at the primary school level, KP suffers from gender disparities, but some improvement over time is visible in Table 3.4. Figure 3.4 is a visual demonstration of disparities disadvantaging girls to varying extents in the poorest, second and middle and fourth Wealth Quintiles in all three MICS KP surveys. However, the sting of suffering

is hard for girls living in the poorest Households/victims of extreme poverty (Yusauf, 2013; Kazmi, 2023a &b, 2024, 2025).

.On the other hand, the children residing in the fourth quintile households (only MICS KP 2017), while the boys and girls in the Richest Households in all three surveys are enjoying a better status in terms of gender parity with a GPI of 1.00 and also triumphed the SDGs 4.5.1 target achievement. However, KP observes some improving trend over time in all wealth quintile households, as shown by the trend in Figure 3.4.

4. COMPARISON OF GP IN KP AND PAKISTAN'S REGIONS/AREAS

Historical comparison of GP under KP's MICS 2017 and 2021 data verifies the existence of gender disparities harming girls in KP and other regions of Pakistan, except AJ&K and Punjab. The analysis of MICS5 data reveals that KP suffers from Gender disparities disadvantaging girls with a GPI of 0.80 is the least performing unit in Pakistan, while AJ&K and Punjab are the best performers with a GPI score of 0.97 each (Table 3.5). MICS round 6 data also demonstrates that KP is not only the lowest performing entity (GPI 0.80) but also maintains its lowest position in Pakistan regions/areas even

after expiry of 13 years (2008-2022) as per MICS survey rounds 5 & 6 reflected in Tables 3.5 & 3.6. The comparison also reveals that KP fails to meet the MDG 3.1 even after the expiry of its deadline of 2015 (Table 3.1). MICS KP wave 6 data also reveal that KP is among the regions/areas still struggling for the SDG 4.5.1 target. A segregated comparison of the regional/areas with KP's urban, rural, division, and district split is deliberated in the next subsections.

4.1 Inter-Regional/Area Comparison:

The data in Tables 3.5 and 3.6 provide a detailed account of GP attainment by the regions/areas, including KPs' success and failure in attaining MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1 targets. In terms of MDG 3.1, KP is the least performing entity with a GPI of 0.80 in 2010 (MICS KP 2010). It also fails to achieve the MDG 3.1 target stipulated in 2015. It is the poorest performer among the Pakistan regions/areas, hosting 20 girls out of school (OOS) against 100 boys in school, against

Table 3.5: Comparison of GPI in Provinces and AJ&K MICS 5

Indicator	Pakistan MDG Set Target 3.1	AJ&K* (2008)	Punjab* (2014)	Sindh* (2014)	Balochistan* (2010)	KP* (2010)
GPI at the Primary School level	1.00	0.97**	0.97**	0.86	0.83	0.80

Source: *Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) AJ&K 2008, "Key Finding Reports" Bureau of Statistics (BoS), P&DD GoAJ&K,2009; MICS Balochistan 2010, BoS, P&DD, Go Balochistan; MICS Punjab-2014, BoS, P&DD, Go Punjab; MICS KP-2016/17, BoS, P&DD, GoKP; MICS Sindh - 2014, Planning and Development Board Sindh, Govt. Sindh.

** GPI varied in 0.97 and 1.03 (UNESCO, 2010, p.2)

14 in Sindh and 17 in Balochistan as reflected in Table 3.5. This study extended evaluation of MICS KP 2021 data finds that KP with a GPI of 0.80 fails to meet the SDG 4.5.1 target (GPI 1.00). It also earned a zero gain in the subsequent MICS KP 2017 and MICS KP 2021 waves, and stands poorer than Punjab and Balochistan, each gaining 0.02 percentage points, and Sindh and AJ&K each with an increase of 0.03 percentage points in the MICS wave 6. The average yearly zero gain in GP indicates that KP could hardly achieve the SDGs 4.5.1 target within the stipulated time (2030). It may need special focus on Newly Merged Districts (NMDs) where GPI varies between 0.20-0.70 (Table 3.2). Farooq and Kia (2016), and Kazmi et al. (2024 & 25), referring to PSLM (2010-11) data, mentioned GPI of FATA and KP separately with GPI of 0.52

and 0.69, respectively, indicating that the merging of FATA districts may imply in retaining of KP's GPI score of 0.80 in 2017 and 2021. Therefore, a special focus on these Newly Merged Districts (NMDs) is urgently needed to access the SDG 4.5.1 targets at the earliest in KP regions.

4.2 Urban-Rural Areas Regional Comparison

The sting of gender disparities in urban areas of KP, with a GPI of 0.80, is harder than in Balochistan, with a GPI of 0.95, demonstrating only 5 girls OOS compared to 20 in KP, against 100 boys in the school. Its working is worse than AJ&K, Punjab, Sindh and Balochistan but slightly better than GB (0.87), the lowest performer in the urban context as reflected in Table 3.6.

Table 3.6: Comparison of Gender Parity at Primary School Level with Provinces/Areas As per MICS 6 Data

Indicator Province/areas MICS6	Punjab MICS6 2017	Sindh MICS6 2020	KP MICS6 2021	Balochistan MICS6 2022	AJ&K MICS6 2021	GB MICS5 2017
Total	0.99	0.89	0.80	0.85	1.00	0.86
Urban	1.02	1.03	0.90	0.95	1.01	0.87
Rural	0.97	0.71	0.80	0.77	1.00	0.85

Source: MICS AJ&K 2020-21, BoS, P&DD GoAJ&K (p-240); MICS Balochistan 2016-17, BOS, P&DD Govt. of Balochistan (p-199); MICS GB 2017-18, P&DD Govt. of Gilgit Baltistan (p-181); MICS KP 2017, BoS P&DD GoKP, (p-182); MICS Punjab BoS, P&DD Govt. of Punjab; MICS Sindh 2018- 19, BoS, Planning & Development Board Govt. of Sindh (p-184)

The rural areas, on the other hand, in most of the regions/areas of Pakistan experience worse conditions than urban areas in the Gender Parity. KP is a better performer than some regions/areas with a GPI of 0.80s. Figure 3.5 and Table 3.6 exhibit KP's performance in rural areas, implying that it fails in achieving the SDG 4.5.1 stipulated target. Its GP score (0.80) is better than Sindh

(0.71) and Balochistan (0.77) but lags behind AJ&K (1.00), Punjab (0.99) and GB (0.85). Moreover, it has 20 OOS girls against Balochistan and Sindh with 23 and 29 OOS girls, respectively, than the 100 boys in the school (Table 3.6 and Fig. 3.5).

In total terms, KP stands deficient in MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1 targets at the provincial level as well as in Urban and Rural domains (Tables 3.5 and 3.6), but

4.3 Divisional and District Levels Comparison

The condition in KP at the divisional and district levels is almost similar to urban-rural segregation. Although a few divisions and districts gained the SDG 4.5.1 (GPI 1.00) and UNESCO's GPI Score (97-1.03) yet most of these widely lacked in accomplishing the earmarked scores in KP. The focus of this section is, therefore, mainly on divisional and district-level performance. It compares the KP's profile with Pakistan's other 5 entities in the divisional and district spheres. It also identifies the best or the worst divisions and districts in KP, and regions/ areas of Pakistan in GP.

4.3.1 Divisional Comparison:

The segregated divisional account of KP regions, along with other entities of Pakistan, is shown in Figure 3.6. It depicts that only the Mardan division among the 8 divisions of KP gets the SDG 4.5.1 targeted GP score “1.00” in 2021. The rest of the 7 divisions suffer from gender disparity, harming girls to a varying extent, with a uniform GP score of 0.80 in six divisions, while the Bannu division among these stands as the poorest unit with a GPI of 0.60. In Pakistan’s 36 divisions, only 3 (8%) divisions met the SDG 4.5.1 target GPI “1.00” successfully, and one of these is in KP, one in Punjab (Sahiwal) and one

in AJ&K (Muzaffarabad). All three divisions get the SDG 4.5.1 target almost a decade before the deadline of 2030. In the rest of the 33 divisions among 36 divisions in 6 regions/areas, 7 divisions of KP lack GP and the SDG 4.5.1 target. Moreover, 12 (including the above-mentioned 3 divisions with GPI 1.00) in 36 divisions get a UNESCO’s (2010) earmarked score for G score between 0.97 and 1.03, a UNESCO’s (2010) earmarked score for GP, while the other 24 lack the GP and thus suffer from gender disparities harming girls (22 divisions) and boys (02 divisions) as given in Figure. 3.6.

4.3.2 District-wise Comparison in KP:

Figure 3.7 reproduces a district-level disaggregated comparison, revealing that 11 out of 149 districts of Pakistan attain the SDG 4.5.1 target (GPI 1.00) while the rest of the 138 districts are deficient in it (Figure 3.4). Among these, 11 districts gained the SDG 4.5.1 in 2021, wherein KP shares 05 districts, including Abbottabad, Chitral, Haripur, Malakand, and Swabi, each with a precise GPI “1.00”. In the other 6 successful districts, Punjab hosts 04, while Balochistan and AJ&K get one each. KP by attaining 16% district success in the SDG 4.5.1 target at the district level, also leads all 6 regions/areas, including Punjab (11%), AJ&K

and GB (10%) and Balochistan (3.5%) and Sindh with zero (Kazmi et al., 2025). In 27 deficient districts of KP, a worse situation prevails in the newly developed/merged districts (NMDs), formerly part of ex-FATA (UNWOMEN, 2020; Kazmi et al., 2024 and 2025). The North Waziristan (GPI 20) districts witness 80 OOS girls against 100 boys in school, the highest number in Pakistan's provinces/areas. GPI score is so low that it places KP as the least performing unit in six regions/areas of Pakistan, having implications for the overall GP score of KP and Pakistan. Therefore, North Waziristan (GPI 20) needs focused interventions from the KP and Pakistan’s government to ameliorate the harmful

trend disadvantaging girls in KP and Pakistan (UNWOMEN, 2020; Kazmi et al, 2024 & 2025).

Overall, at the regional level, KP stands as the poorest entity, maintaining its status over time in both the MICS KP rounds 5 and 6 (GPI 0.80) surveys. At the urban level, it again maintains its

rank as a lower performer with a slight increase in GPI (0.90) against GB (0.87), but remains behind AJ&K (GPI 1.00), Punjab (1.02), Sindh (1.03) and Balochistan (0.95). Under divisional

Table 3.7: Percentage Achievement in Gender Parity at Primary School Level (%)

Region/Area	AJ&K	Punjab	GB	KP	Balochistan	Sindh
Division	100%	60%	33%	14%	14%	0%
District	80%	36%	30%	16%	6%	7%

Source: Prepared from MICS Waves 6 Regional/Areas Data

and district level comparisons referring to UNESCO (2010) GPI range (0.97 - 1.03), KP enjoys the 4th position with 14% and 16% success at division and district levels, respectively (Table 3.7). Table 3.7 further underlines that it [KP] leads Balochistan and Sindh, having 14% and 1%, and zero and 7% achievement respectively, but lags behind AJ&K, enjoying 100% and 80%, Punjab 60% and 36%, and GB 33% and 30% success at the division and district level respectively.

6. FINDINGS:

Both the MDGs 3.1. and SDG 4.5.1 are achievable targets even in poor regions/areas with better resource inputs, ensuring their optimal utilization and community support, but these remain inaccessible in many regions/areas of Pakistan, including KP. Despite a persistent uncondusive environment since 1947, Pakistan is making some improvements in education indices and thus some of its regions/areas attained gender parity, referring to the MDG 3.1 and

SDG 4.5.1 targets (ASER, 2019 & 2020; PAGE, 2021; Govt. of Punjab, 2022; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). The gender disparities are persistently disadvantaging girls in KP and other regions/areas, which stem from illiterate mothers or living in the poorest households/suffering from extreme poverty. Gender disparities also persist in most of deficient regions/areas like KP due to fragile government support, lethargic community, resource constraints, punitive sociocultural norms, patriarchal mindset, son preference, female say/role family and society, limited access to school, a few girls' schools, deficient female staff, poor infrastructure with missing facilities, female education, early/child marriage, deficient transport, lacking security, unemployment, extreme poverty, big family size, etc. Many of these factors are not relevant to AJ&K due to their lesser role (Kazmi et al., 2023a & b; Kazmi et al., 2024). Despite lacking in many areas, KP observes some improvement in the Gender Parity profile at the regional, urban-rural, division

and district levels, though it lags behind Punjab and AJ&K in many aspects. Like most other regions, KP fails to attain the MDG 3.1 until 2015 and the SDG 4.5.1 until 2021. Merging of FATA districts implies KP's progress in gender parity, retaining its GP score (0.80) at the 2010 level when FATA districts were not part of KP (MICS KP 2010). KP makes good strides to retain the GP score of 0.80, even with the poor performance of the ex-FATA districts. Newly Merged Districts (NMDs) and other passive districts in KP need more inference, as the marginal effect would be better there. Nevertheless, the well-performing districts should also be given due weight to maintain their pace in GP gains and cover the shortfall in deficient districts. KP is the 2nd last in the urban domain with a GPI of 0.90, following Balochistan with a GPI of 0.95, but leading GB, having a GPI of 0.87. It stands among the poorest performers with more (10) OOS girls in its urban areas than 0.05 in Balochistan urban areas, against 100 boys in the school. The situation of keeping KP stagnant demands concentrated moves to deal with an odd situation. The sting of gender bias disadvantaging girls in KP rural areas is less than that of Sindh and Balochistan, having 29 and 23 OOS girls respectively against 20 OOS girls in KP, than 100 boys in school. Although KP improved GPI at urban and rural levels, but lacks in gaining the SDGs target 4.5.1 at the Regional, Urban and Rural levels. KP at the divisional level stands as the lowest performer with 4th position in regions/areas. Only one of its 8 divisions enjoys GP and attains the SDG 4.5.1 target, while 7 divisions suffer from Gender disparities harming girls. Similarly, only 5 districts gain a Gender Parity score (1.00), fulfilling the SDG 4.5.1 target. The KP is the best performer with 50% success among a total of 10 successful districts accomplishing the SDG 4.5.1 target in Pakistan. Both the mother's illiteracy and the poorest household status persistently hinder GP achievement in KP and in other regions/areas of Pakistan (Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). Urban bias education policies and interventions also deprive the rural segment of girl students and thus affect the overall GP

in KP. The underprivileged working conditions of KP call for focused intervention to deal with the situation, which makes KP the worst performer in Pakistan. Teachers' training also plays a vital role in addressing gender disparity in Pakistan and its regions (Shabbir and Wei, 2016 & 2015). Moreover, the above-cited critical issues require proper handling to achieve gender parity in KP and passive regions of Pakistan (Umer and Zahid, 2017; UNESCAP, 2018; Govt. of Punjab, 2022; Baran and Bend, 2023; Kazmi et al., 2023a&b; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025).

7. CONCLUSIONS

Both the MDG 3.1 and SDG 4.5.1 are attainable targets with strong government commitment and community support along with better access to schools, soft socio-cultural norms, better education facilities, mother education, family opulence, enhanced female role in family and society, > son preference, etc., (Noreen, 2023; Kazmi et al., 2023a & b). Financial paucity does not matter in attaining GP, referring to MDG and SDG like committed targets (WEF, 2021; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). Effective management of financial scarcity, ensuring optimal use of scarce resources, also helps in rapid gains in GP score (Tahir 2017; Kazmi et al., 2024). A special focus on female education, targeting illiterate mothers and the poorest households, could pay dividends in improving gender parity across regions/areas (Yusuf, 2013; Zulqurnain and Hussain, 2016; Imran, 2017; Umer and Zahid, 2017; Kazmi et al., 2023a&b). Strict cultural norms and social binding need to be softened with instant curative measures/management in distressed areas, divisions and districts in KP and other deprived regions/areas (Yusuf, 2013; Kazmi et al., 2023a&b; Noreen, 2023; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). Strong government commitment and community support need to be in place to remove the gender gap harming girls in deficient areas, divisions and districts of Pakistan regions/areas (UMWOMEN, Kazmi et al., 2.23 a&b, 2024 & 2025). The community needs motivation through special initiatives to play its pivotal role in promoting gender parity in

underprovided regions/areas (Kazmi et al., 2023a&b; Kazmi et al., 2024). More concentrated efforts are needed in rural areas to achieve the SDG 4.5.1 target in deficient regions/areas, especially KP. Policy realignment focusing on firm interventions is obligatory for taming education access, improving teaching-learning environment, ornamenting infrastructure, improving girls-focused interventions (free books, security, school uniforms, transport and launch) and ensuring quick gains in the SDG 4.5.1 (Haq, 2016, Umer & Zahid, 2017, Iqbal 2022; Govt. of Punjab, 2022; Kazmi et al 2023a&b; Kazmi et al., 2024). Judicious budgetary allocation with its optimal utilization is pivotal for improving education indices, including gender parity (Tahir, 2017; Kazmi et al., 2023a&b; Baran and Bend, 2023; Kazmi et al., 2024). Diverse actions focused on the least performed areas/divisions/districts could pay dividends in preventing the broadening gender gap in KP and other regions/areas. The insight from previous research work could also help reduce the gender disparities harming the girls. Gender-focused economic and educational policies/reforms can pay dividends in all deficient regions/areas, including KP (Haq, 2016; Umer and Zahid, 2017; Kazmi et al., 2023a&b; Kazmi et al., 2024). Gender based interventions also need to be redirected to secluded, deprived and remote parts of KP and other areas, particularly to rural areas, the disadvantaged segments and deprived districts (CIET, 1997; Brohi and Kakepoto, 2013; Umer and Zahid, 2017; Kazmi et al., 2024). More girls' schools and female teachers, along with Teacher Training programs focusing on female faculty, could also help address the prevailing Gender Gap (UNWMEN, 2020; Kazmi et al., 2024 & 2025). Strict law enforcement to protect women's rights could assist in achieving the SDG 4.5.1 target. Rectifying political maneuvering and enhancing female roles in family and society, community engagement, public private partnership could also pay dividends in KP in attaining the universal Gender Parity and the SDG 4.5.1 target (Yusauf, 2013; Brohi and Kakepoto, 2013; Haq, 2016; UNWOMEN, 2020; Govt.

of Punjab, 2022; Noreen, 2023; UNESCO, 2022; Kami et al., 2023 a&b, 2024 2025).

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